

Behaviour of Halogenated Nitrobenzenes with β -Diketones. Part V. Benzoyl Derivatives of Substituted Anthranils and Their Conversion to Quinazolones

I. R. Gambhir and S. S. Joshi

Halogenated nitrobenzoylanthranils, obtained by benzylation of nitroanthranils, have been cyclised to 2-phenylquinazolones by heating with a few amino compounds.

In a previous communication¹, preparation of a number of halogenated nitroanthranils was described. The behaviour of these halogenated nitroanthranils (I) on benzylation has been found to be similar to that of 6-nitroanthranil². These form 4-nitro-*N*-benzoylanthranilic acids (II) and 4-nitrobenzoylanthranils (III) when heated with benzoyl chloride in presence of pyridine.

[a; X=Cl; b; X=Br; g; X=I]

On heating with ammonia, aniline, toluidines, etc., these are converted into *o*-arylaminonitrobenzamides (IV); the latter cyclise to the corresponding 2-phenylquinazolones (V) when heated alone above their melting points. In glacial acetic acid solution with hydrazine acetate and hydroxylamino, 3-amino- and 3-hydroxy-2-phenylquinazolones are formed directly; no intermediate *o*-arylaminonitrobenzamides could be isolated. The

1. Joshi and Gambhir, *this issue*, p. 43.
2. *Idem*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 3714.

aminoquinazolones are basic in character, whereas the hydroxy derivatives are acidic. These are recovered unchanged from their salts with concentrated hydrochloric acid and caustic soda, respectively, when made alkaline or acidic.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Chloro-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil (IIIa) and *6-Chloro-4-nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic Acid* (IIa).—These were prepared by heating anthranil (Ia) with benzoyl chloride and pyridine at 130° for 3 hours. The anthranil (IIIa) was extracted with acetic acid in 53% yield as lemon-yellow cubes, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 55.29; H, 2.29. $C_{14}H_9O_4N_2Cl$ requires C, 55.54; H, 2.31%).

The mother-liquor after separation of (IIIa) provided (IIa) in 38% yield as colorless needles from dilute ethanol, m.p. 261°. (Found: N, 8.69. $C_{14}H_9O_5N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.74%).

6-Bromo-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil (IIIb) and *6-bromo-4-nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid* (IIb) were prepared from compound (Ib) by the procedure given for (IIIa). The compound (IIIb) was obtained on extraction with acetic acid in 55% yield as yellow plates, m.p. 190°. (Found: C, 48.60; H, 2.00. $C_{14}H_9O_4N_2Br$ requires C, 48.41; H, 2.02%).

The mother-liquor provided 38% of the corresponding 6-bromo-4-nitro-*N*-acid (IIb) as colorless needles from dilute ethanol, m.p. 255°. (Found: N, 7.52. $C_{14}H_9O_5N_2Br$ requires N, 7.67%).

6-Iodo-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil (IIIc) and *6-iodo-4-nitrobenzoylanthranilic acid* (IIc) were obtained similarly from compound (Ic). The anthranil (IIIc) was recrystallised from acetic acid in 49% yield as dirty yellow plates, m.p. 184°. (Found: C, 42.53; H, 1.74. $C_{14}H_9O_4N_2I$ requires C, 42.64; H, 1.78%).

The mother-liquor furnished 33% of the acid (IIc) as colorless needles from ethanol, m.p. 251°. (Found: N, 6.71. $C_{14}H_9O_5N_2I$ requires N, 6.79%).

6-Chloro-4-nitro-2-benzoylamino-benzamide (IVa).—A solution of the anthranil (IIIa) (0.5 g.) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was boiled under reflux and dry ammonia was passed into it. A white crystalline mass separated which on recrystallisation from acetic acid provided 81% of the benzamide (IVa) as colorless needles, m.p. 240°. (Found: C, 52.22; H, 3.16. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4N_3Cl$ requires C, 52.58; H, 3.13%).

5-Chloro-7-nitro-2-phenylquinazol-4-one (Va).—The preceding amide (IVa) (0.5 g.) was heated at 250° for an hour. The product after being successively washed with hot water and ethanol was extracted with a mixture of ethanol and ethyl acetate. The extract after purification with activated charcoal furnished 53% of the quinazolone (Va) as colorless cubes, m.p. 311°. (Found: C, 55.48; H, 2.62. $C_{14}H_8O_3N_3Cl$ requires C, 55.73; H, 2.65%).

6-Chloro-4-nitro-2-benzoylamino-benzanilide was obtained by heating (IIIa) with aniline at 150° for 2 hours. Extraction with acetic acid provided 70% of the anilide as buff prisms, m.p. 236°. (Found: C, 60.47; H, 3.50. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_3Cl$ requires C, 60.68; H, 3.53%).

5-Chloro-7-nitro-2,3-diphenylquinazol-4-one was obtained by heating the preceding anilide at 250° for 2 hours. Recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 48% of the pure

quinazolone as colorless needles, m.p. 176°. (Found: C, 63.32; H, 3.15. $C_{20}H_{12}O_3N_3Cl$ requires C, 63.57; H, 3.17%).

6-Chloro-4-nitro-2-benzylaminobenzophenylhydrazide was prepared by heating (IIIa) with phenylhydrazine for 2 hours. The hydrazide was crystallised from dilute ethanol in 69% yield as dirty white plates, m.p. 194°. (Found: C, 58.21; H, 3.62. $C_{20}H_{15}O_4N_4Cl$ requires C, 58.46; H, 3.65%).

3-Anilino-5-chloro-7-nitro-2-phenylquinazol-4-one—The preceding chloronitrohydrazide was heated at 220° for 1 hour. Recrystallisation from dilute ethanol afforded 48% of the quinazolone as light brown crystals, m.p. 156°. (Found: C, 60.88; H, 3.29. $C_{20}H_{13}O_3N_4Cl$ requires C, 61.15; H, 3.31%).

3-Amino-5-chloro-7-nitro-2-phenylquinazol-4-one was prepared by heating (IIIa) with hydrazine hydrate in glacial acetic acid. It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid as pale yellow crystals, m.p. 252°. (Found: C, 52.81; H, 2.79. $C_{14}H_9O_3N_4Cl$ requires C, 53.08; H, 2.84%).

3-Hydroxy-5-chloro-7-nitro-2-phenylquinazol-4-one was obtained similarly as above, using hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate. Recrystallisation from dilute acetic acid furnished 56% of the product as pale yellow crystals, m.p. 234°. (Found: C, 52.71; H, 2.48. $C_{14}H_8O_4N_3Cl$ requires C, 52.90; H, 2.52%).

TABLE I

Benzanilides from 6-chloro-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil.

No.	6-Chloro-4-nitro-2-benzoylaminobenzo-	M.P.	Colour.	%Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	-o-toluidide	204°	Buff	63	61.50	61.55	3.86	3.90
2	-m-toluidide	213°	Dirty white	61	61.41	61.55	3.85	3.90
3	-p-toluidide	240°	Colorless	65	61.27	61.55	3.88	3.90
4	-o-chloroanilide	228°	"	59	55.59	55.81	2.99	3.02
5	-m-chloroanilide	247°	Pale yellow	60	55.45	55.81	3.00	3.02
6	-p-chloroanilide	225°	Colorless	64	55.71	55.81	3.07	3.02
7	- α -naphthylamide	267°	"	67	64.33	64.65	3.55	3.59
8	- β -naphthylamide	273°	Pale yellow	69	64.28	64.65	3.56	3.59

TABLE II

*Quinazolones from 6-chloro-4-nitro-2-benzoylaminobenzanilides.**

No.	5-Chloro-4-nitro-2-benzoylaminobenzanil-3-yl-quinazol-4-one.	M.P.	Colour.	%Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	-o-tolyl	160°	Colorless	42	64.06	64.37	3.52	3.57
2	-m-tolyl	161°	Light brown	40	64.35	64.37	3.51	3.57
3	-p-tolyl	175°	Colorless	44	64.10	64.37	3.51	3.57
4	-o-chlorophenyl	170°	Buff	39	58.11	58.25	2.63	2.67
5	-m-chlorophenyl	163°	Colorless	39	58.42	58.25	2.68	2.67
6	-p-chlorophenyl	169°	Dirty white	41	58.06	58.25	2.64	2.67
7	- α -naphthyl	183°	Pale yellow	45	67.11	67.36	3.22	3.27
8	- β -naphthyl	200°	Yellow	47	67.04	67.38	3.25	3.27

*Vide Table I,

TABLE III

Benzoylaminobenzanilides from 6-bromo-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil.

No.	6-Bromo-4-nitro-2-benzoylaminobenzo-	M.P.	Colour.	% Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	-amide	245°	Colorless	82	45.92	46.15	2.73	2.75
2	-anilide	252°	„	70	54.27	54.54	3.14	3.18
3	-o-toluidide	223°	„	61	55.20	55.51	3.50	3.52
4	-m-toluidide	234°	„	62	55.10	55.51	3.57	3.52
5	-p-toluidide	254°	Light grey	64	55.20	55.51	3.50	3.52
6	-o-chloroanilide	237°	Colorless	58	50.27	50.58	2.70	2.74
7	-m-chloroanilide	250°	Buff	58	50.30	50.58	2.80	2.74
8	-p-chloroanilide	240°	Colorless	60	50.15	50.58	2.72	2.74
9	- α -naphthylamide	284°	„	64	58.39	58.77	3.21	3.26
10	- β -naphthylamide	272°	Pale yellow	69	58.48	58.77	3.28	3.26
11	-phenylhydrazide	215°	Buff	65	52.20	52.75	3.22	3.29

TABLE IV

*Quinazolones from 6-bromo-4-nitro-2-benzoylaminobenzamides **

No.	5-Bromo-7-nitro-2-phenyl-3-....quinazol-4-one.	M.P.	Colour.	% Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Do	318°	Colorless	51	48.37	49.55	2.29	2.31
2	-phenyl-	184°	„	48	56.48	56.87	2.79	2.84
3	-o-tolyl-	157°	Dirty white	40	57.64	57.79	3.19	3.21
4	-m-tolyl-	145°	Colorless	41	57.48	57.79	3.20	3.21
5	-p-tolyl-	162°	„	44	57.57	57.79	3.23	3.21
6	-o-chlorophenyl-	154°	„	40	52.35	52.57	2.38	2.41
7	-m-chlorophenyl-	160°	Pale yellow	39	52.42	52.57	2.46	2.41
8	-p-chlorophenyl	165°	Colorless	41	52.60	52.57	2.37	2.41
9	- α -naphthyl-	189°	Buff	45	61.19	61.02	2.93	2.98
10	- β -naphthyl-	211°	Yellow	48	60.69	61.02	2.94	2.96
11	-anilino-	158°	Dirty white	45	54.68	54.92	2.95	2.97
12	-amino-	240°	Pale yellow	78	46.31	46.54	2.52	2.49
13	-hydroxy-	214°	„	61	46.50	46.41	2.18	2.21

*Vide Table III.

TABLE V

Benzoylaminobenzanilides from 6-iodo-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil.

No.	6-Iodo-4-nitro-2-benzoylaminobenzo-	M.P.	Colour.	% Yield.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	-amide	257°	Colorless	72	40.61	40.88	2.40	2.43
2	-anilide	249°	Pale yellow	64	49.06	49.28	2.85	2.87
3	-o-toluidide	206°	„	54	50.00	50.30	3.22	3.19
4	-m-toluidide	209°	Yellow	50	50.11	50.30	3.18	3.19
5	-p-toluidide	250°	Light brown	57	50.51	50.30	3.23	3.19
6	-o-chloroanilide	219°	Pale yellow	51	45.72	46.02	2.54	2.49
7	-m-chloroanilide	247°	Brown	51	45.68	46.02	2.44	2.49
8	-p-chloroanilide	252°	Light brown	54	45.80	46.02	2.46	2.49
9	- α -naphthylamide	264°	Yellow	50	53.36	53.63	2.93	2.98
10	- β -naphthylamide	279°	„	62	53.42	53.63	2.96	2.98
11	-phenylhydrazide	201°	Light brown	60	47.50	47.81	2.92	2.99

TABLE VI

*Quinazolones from 6-iodo-4-nitro-2-benzoylaminobenzamides.**

No.	5-Iodo-7-nitro-2-phenyl-3-quinazol-4-one.	M.P.	Colour.	%Yield.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Do	321°	Light brown	46	42.40	42.75	2.01	2.04
2	-phenyl-	190°	"	40	51.32	51.17	2.56	2.56
3	-o-tolyl-	162°	"	32	52.29	52.17	2.85	2.90
4	-m-tolyl-	147°	Brown	29	51.87	52.17	2.96	2.90
5	-p-tolyl-	165°	Yellow	34	52.50	52.17	2.85	2.90
6	-o-chlorophenyl-	150°	"	26	47.35	47.66	2.02	2.18
7	-m-chlorophenyl-	160°	Light brown	30	47.40	47.66	2.13	2.18
8	-p-chlorophenyl-	181°	Yellow	32	47.54	47.66	2.20	2.18
9	- α -naphthyl-	193°	"	33	55.18	55.40	2.66	2.69
10	- β -naphthyl-	209°	"	37	55.30	55.40	2.71	2.69
11	-anilino-	159°	Brown	36	40.16	49.59	2.64	2.68
12	-amino-	252°	Yellow	71	41.36	41.18	2.28	2.20
13	-hydroxy-	231°	"	54	40.87	41.08	1.90	1.95

*Vide Table V.

A few *o*-acylaminobenzanilides were obtained from 6-chloro-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil (Table I), 6-bromo-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil (Table III), 6-iodo-4-nitrobenzoylanthranil (Table V) and aromatic amino compounds. These furnished the corresponding quinazolono derivatives (Tables II, IV, VI) when heated about 30° above their melting points.

SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY,
MEERUT COLLEGE,
MEERUT.

Received May 7, 1963.